

Physical Artificial Intelligence: From Perception to Autonomy - Foundations, Learning, and Social Implications

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Abstract

This article examines the conceptual foundations, technical architecture, learning strategies, and social implications of Physical Artificial Intelligence (Physical AI) or Embodied AI. Unlike traditional AI systems, which operate within the boundaries of digital environments, Physical AI integrates perception, cognition, and action to exist as embodied agents in the real world. The article presents sensor technologies, deep learning architectures, simulation-to-reality training strategies, and multimodal self-supervised learning as key elements for adaptive autonomy. Practical applications in the fields of medicine, manufacturing, and public safety are introduced to illustrate current advances. Finally, the article discusses the economic, social, and ethical risks associated with autonomous decision-making in machines and humanoid robots equipped with embedded AI, arguing that the large-scale adoption of Physical AI represents a societal shift whose consequences must be critically examined.

Keywords: *Physical Artificial Intelligence, Physical AI, sensors, artificial cognition, algorithms, machine learning, deep learning, autonomous agents, society.*

Introduction

We know artificial intelligence (AI) as an essentially invisible service. Its algorithms live inside the digital world, inhabiting it exclusively, confined to computer processors and memory banks and the information flows of the internet. After extensive training phases on colossal volumes of data, AI-based systems are capable of generating climate predictions, classifying emails, recommending films, detecting financial fraud, and creating content that, at first glance, appears indistinguishable from that produced by human beings.

These achievements are impressive and continue to drive transformations across the most varied levels of society. But there is a boundary that AI, until very recently, had never crossed: that of the

physical world. No AI algorithm had ever picked up an object, walked down a street, felt the texture of a surface, or heard the song of birds inside a forest. And there is a profound reason for this. The physical world is fundamentally different from the digital one. It is extremely complex, disorderly, ambiguous, and in a state of permanent transformation and motion. Understanding it is not enough; one must live it in real time, perceive it through sensors, continuously adapting and responding to what changes at every instant. Reading data from the past, however voluminous, does not prepare an AI system for the unpredictability of the real world. This, however, is changing in a radical and accelerating way with the arrival of Physical AI.

The origins of this idea are older than we might imagine. In 1991, Rodney Brooks, a computer scientist and pioneer in the field of robotics,

proposed the radical vision that intelligence did not require complex internal models of the world. Working with autonomous mobile robots at MIT, he arrived at what he called an "unexpected conclusion": "explicit representations and models of the world simply get in the way; it is better to use the world as its own model." (Liu & Wu, 2024). Ten years later, in 2001, scientists Rolf Pfeifer and Christian Scheier deepened this argument in the book *Understanding Intelligence* (Pfeifer & Scheier, 2001), proposing that intelligence is an integrated manifestation of an agent's entire body, its structure, its movements, its concrete relationship with the surrounding environment.

"Physical AI is, in essence, what the academic community defined years ago as embodied AI: a robotic entity that integrates a physical body with an artificial brain, in which advanced artificial intelligence models operate continuously and contextually, enabling perception, action, and decision-making in the real world." (Murer, 2025)

An alternative current of research proposes what has come to be known as World Models: systems that, rather than learning exclusively through a body interacting with the environment, internally construct a mental representation of the world, capable of simulating possible futures, anticipating consequences, and planning actions before executing them (Ha & Schmidhuber, 2018). In this view, the senses are understood as sources of information through which the brain builds a referential model of the external world, and from this model acts upon it.

In contrast to the World Models theory, Physical AI proceeds from a different premise: that the senses are not mere input channels for data, but constitutive elements of intelligence itself. It is through direct sensory experience that human beings and other living organisms actively and continuously construct their understanding of the

world around them. In this paradigm, there is no intelligence without a body endowed with senses, and no useful body without the capacity to act on what it perceives. In the world of machines, this translates into a necessary dependence on devices capable of performing three deeply interrelated functions: sensing the environment, interpreting what has been captured, and acting upon it autonomously. Perception, cognition¹, and action thus become the three pillars that define and distinguish Physical AI from all other forms of AI we know.

In this article, I will use the human body as a reference point, particularly given the rapid evolution of humanoid robotics, to detail the three fundamental pillars of Physical AI. It is important to acknowledge, however, that this field of research has evolved historically from careful observation of how animals, from insects to mammals, perceive, make decisions, and navigate the challenges of the world around them².

Perception, Cognition, and Action

Physical AI draws on theoretical concepts and experiments from two scientific fields: Cognitive Psychology, which studies the mental processes involved in perception, memory, attention, and decision-making; and Neuroscience, which investigates the neural mechanisms that allow living organisms to interact with and adapt to their environment. In what follows, we will examine, albeit in simplified terms, how perception, cognition, and action operate within a continuous sensorimotor cycle, and what strategies computer science and robotics have developed to replicate this dynamic and make Physical AI viable in machines.

¹ I use the term cognition to designate the set of processes by which the brain acquires, processes, stores, and uses information, including attention, memory, reasoning, decision-making, planning, and problem-solving (Neisser, 1967).

² The roots of this approach go back to cybernetics, a field founded by Norbert Wiener in the late 1940s. Wiener defined cybernetics as "the scientific study of control and communication in animals and machines."

When we run our fingertips across the surface of an object like a glass, for example, without looking at it, the nerve impulse generated by the touch takes approximately 20 milliseconds to travel through the peripheral nerves and reach the brain's primary somatosensory area (Allison et al., 1991). Yet this interval of thousandths of a second does not register as a delay for the brain, which simultaneously interprets what is happening at the very moment of contact. The cognitive processes responsible for "recognizing the object" occur in an integrated and simultaneous fashion, drawing on information about position, weight, texture, temperature, shape, and size to construct a mental representation of the glass, without our having to "wait" for our fingers to trace its entire surface. Perception and cognition are not sequential stages; they happen at the same time, as inseparable processes of a single unified system.

But this is precisely where the challenge grows even more complex for Physical AI. It would be natural to imagine that "only after" perceiving and recognizing the glass does the brain then "decide" how to act upon it — a linear sequence of perception, followed by cognition, followed by action. Reality, however, is far more complex and sophisticated than that.

Neuroimaging studies reveal that the primary motor cortex begins to respond while we are still in the process of perceiving the object; motor planning, that is, the next action, does not wait for cognitive processing to conclude, but occurs in parallel (Cisek & Kalaska, 2010). This means that as your fingers move across the surface of the glass, the brain generates an internal "copy" of the motor command and uses it to predict what kind of sensation you should feel in the next instant, actively modulating and coordinating both perception and action themselves (Wolpert & Flanagan, 2001).

Along the same conceptual lines, we encounter the theory of sensorimotor contingencies proposed by O'Regan and Noë (2001). According to the authors, perceiving is not simply "receiving information and then acting" — it is actively exploring the environment, where action continuously reconfigures what will be perceived next. Perception, cognition, and action therefore form a **continuous sensorimotor loop**: a cycle that repeats dozens of times per second, in which each component influences and modulates the others in an inseparable way. It is precisely this circularity, and not a linear chain of processing, that characterizes biological intelligence. Replicating this dynamic in machines is the central challenge of Physical AI. (O'Regan & Noë, 2001) (Cisek & Kalaska, 2010)

Sensors, Algorithms, and Actuators

One of the most ambitious goals of robotics is to endow machines with the ability to perceive their surrounding environment and interact autonomously with objects and other agents³ using their own limbs without the need for human supervision. To achieve this, engineering has over the years developed "sensors." By definition, a sensor "is a device that detects events or changes in its environment and responds to them. Just as human eyes detect light and skin detects pressure, a sensor detects a specific physical quantity, such as temperature, motion, light, humidity, or pressure, and converts that information into a measurable signal." (Fraden, 2010)

Taking the sense of touch as an example, the first decisive milestone came in 1973, when Professor Ichiro Kato of Waseda University in Japan completed the WABOT-1, the first humanoid robot equipped with tactile sensors in its hands. For the first time, a machine could grasp and transport objects with genuine tactile feedback.

³ In the context of Artificial Intelligence and robotics, an *agent* is any system, whether biological or artificial, capable of perceiving its environment through sensors and acting upon it autonomously. Humans, animals, and robots are all examples of agents.

The human sense of touch, however, is extraordinarily sophisticated, capable of simultaneously detecting pressure, temperature, vibration, texture, shape, pain, and the precise position of each finger in space. Today we have the BioTac, used in prosthetics and robotics, which integrates force, vibration, and temperature (Yu et al., 2025). We now also have sophisticated sensors capable of replicating, with varying degrees of sensitivity, vision (cameras and computer vision systems), smell (electronic noses for chemical compound detection), hearing (high-fidelity microphones) (Murer, 2025), and even taste (electronic tongues for the chemical analysis of food) (Ciosek & Wróblewski, 2014).

For the signals captured by each sensor to be understood by a machine or robot, however, they must be processed and interpreted computationally. This is where **artificial cognition** comes in: the set of algorithms that employ machine learning techniques, in particular deep learning, which is built on artificial neural networks with multiple processing layers. This digital architecture was inspired, albeit in a highly simplified way, by the neuronal architecture of the brain. This reference to the anatomy and functional mode of the brain has proven, on the one hand, ideal for achieving more effective and efficient algorithms, and on the other, a colossal challenge, since even neuroscience and cognitive psychology have yet to fully explain the brain, its neurons, and human intelligence.

The defining characteristic of artificial neural networks is their capacity to learn through training on massive quantities of data and to recognize patterns within that data, making iterative adjustments across millions of internal parameters⁴. In the context of this article, signals captured by sensors, such as the pixels of an image recorded by a camera, or pressure readings from a robotic finger, are transformed into high-level abstract representations, such as "this is an

image of a person" or "the smooth surface of a glass."

Finally, there are actuators: components that provide the capacity to perform action, both locomotion and manipulation, bringing the robot's mechanical parts to life through servomotors, drives, and transmissions (Siciliano et al., 2009). Without actuators, machines and robots would remain inert, with no ability to act upon or modify the environment around them.

Historically, in the early days of industrial robotics, actuators performed repetitive, pre-programmed movements in highly controlled environments, such as automotive assembly lines, and in most manufacturing industries, this remains the reality today. With the advent of social and humanoid robots, however, the technical requirements have evolved drastically: the demand shifted from mere force and precision to include fine torque control, enabling the manipulation of more delicate objects in varying shapes, weights, and textures. In parallel, the use of reinforcement learning techniques is transforming robot locomotion, allowing machines to move with greater agility and adaptability by learning to walk, run, or jump across complex and unfamiliar terrain.

Adaptive Autonomy

The earliest conceptions of what we today call robots trace back to Ancient Greece, when engineers and philosophers were already envisioning automata capable of reproducing movements resembling those of living beings. These devices appeared both in mechanical designs and in mythological narratives, in which artificial figures carried out specific tasks and, in some accounts, demonstrated a certain degree of autonomy or decision-making capacity.

⁴ Internal parameters refer to the weights and biases that determine the strength of the connections between artificial neurons. During training, optimization algorithms iteratively adjust these values to minimize the error between the network's predictions and the expected results. Modern deep learning networks can contain millions to billions of adjustable parameters.

It was the Industrial Revolution, however, that definitively established automated machines as an integral part of the productive chain. From that period onward, automation moved out of the realm of technical speculation and came to occupy a central role in manufacturing. In contemporary industrial robotics, we find systems capable of executing multiple operations with high precision, based on sequential programming and rigorously defined control logic. These robots operate in highly structured and predictable environments, within delimited areas protected by safety devices.

Up to this point, we are dealing with fixed machines, with little or no capacity for autonomous locomotion or deliberative planning. In the 1960s, however, the first robots with these capabilities began to emerge. The most advanced of its time was Shakey, developed by SRI International between 1966 and 1972. Shakey was capable of perceiving its environment through cameras and sensors, constructing a symbolic representation of the space around it, and using that representation to navigate, planning actions by means of formal logic (Nilsson, 1984).

It is in this context that we encounter, for the first time, AI applied to robotics: a machine becoming capable of going beyond merely reacting to external stimuli, and instead formulating plans and actions to achieve goals based on an abstract description of the world. This gave rise to the concept of automatic planning (AI planning), establishing one of the fundamental pillars connecting computational representation and physical action in the real world.

There was, however, a problem with the architecture of this generation of robots. Like Shakey, they were based on symbolic AI and deliberative planning, that is, they followed a classical cycle that can be summarized as: *perceive* → *model* → *plan* → *act*. This model, despite being innovative, proved fragile in dynamic and

unpredictable environments, as the robot would fail when confronted with unexpected changes.

In the 1980s, Rodney Brooks, a computer scientist and robotics specialist at MIT, proposed a break with this paradigm by creating the concept of **subsumption architecture**⁵, arguing that intelligence and adaptive behavior could emerge from simple layers of reactive behaviors, without the need for centralized symbolic representation. "A control system for a completely autonomous mobile robot must perform many complex information-processing tasks in real time. It operates in an environment where the boundary conditions (considering the instantaneous control problem in a classical formulation of control theory) are changing rapidly." (Brooks, 1986)

When we bring these two approaches together, the reactive and the deliberative, which allow a machine or robot to respond to environmental changes and plan toward objectives, we arrive at a new concept: that of the **autonomous agent**. According to Pattie Maes, "autonomous agents are computational systems that inhabit complex dynamic environments, perceive and act continuously, and direct their actions toward achieving goals or maintaining desired internal states." (Maes, 1995). A similar definition comes from computer scientist José Brustoloni: "Autonomous agents are systems capable of autonomous and intentional action in the real world." (Brustoloni, 1991). Both definitions reflect the defining characteristic of autonomous agents: the capacity to act upon the environment using embedded artificial cognition, which in turn enables them to make decisions with or without human supervision.

For an autonomous agent to be capable of making decisions within the environment it inhabits, however, it requires a reference knowledge base — information about the real world through which it must navigate, perceive changes, reason, and act. Even more critically, it needs to be able to

⁵ In this architecture, the overall task is divided into subtasks that are executed by behaviors organized in hierarchical layers. (Santos, 2017)

receive updates in the face of novel situations and process them in real time.

The question that then arises is: how is this knowledge base constructed? It is at this point that one of the most complex challenges in Physical AI enters the picture: learning in the real world.

Real-World Learning

Every AI system or model depends on data — this is the raw material through which they acquire knowledge. When immersed in the digital world, as is the case with large language models (LLMs), this raw material is readily available, for example in the billions of text pages published on the internet⁶. But for Physical AI, the data used to teach a robot to move, grasp, and adapt are of a different nature entirely. This data must represent the real world in which we live. Textual descriptions or static images of objects are not sufficient; for example, it is necessary to capture information about how interaction with objects actually occurs: forces applied during contact, spatial trajectories of movements, material deformations, and the dynamic consequences of each action. The physical laws governing motion, such as gravity, friction, inertia, and conservation of momentum, must be internalized by the robotic system, whether through explicit learning or accumulated experience. Furthermore, with the advancement of high-resolution tactile sensors, it has become necessary to calibrate not only pressure and force, but also temperature, surface texture, slip, and material properties such as rigidity, elasticity, and viscosity.

To overcome this challenge, Physical AI employs different training strategies. Among the most prominent are:

- **Imitation learning**, in which the robot learns from human demonstrations, whether through teleoperation, motion capture, or kinesthetic teaching, internalizing action patterns through observation;
- **Sim-to-real** with domain randomization, a technique that introduces systematic variations in the physical and sensory parameters of the simulation, such as mass, lighting, texture, friction, and sensor noise, with the goal of reducing the gap between simulation and reality and facilitating the transfer of the trained model to the real world; (Muratore et al., 2022)
- **Multimodal self-supervised learning**, which integrates multiple sensory sources, such as computer vision, proprioception, and tactile sensors, allowing the robot to extract supervisory signals from its own interaction with the environment.

Despite the advances provided by these approaches, in imitation learning and multimodal self-supervised learning methods, data collection and manipulation are extremely costly, time-consuming, and potentially risky: each manipulation attempt requires physical hardware, consumes operational time, and can result in mechanical wear or damage to the robot, the human operator, and the environment. An emerging strategy, which can be understood as an evolution of Sim-to-real, has gained prominence: the generation of synthetic data in high-fidelity virtual environments. This method uses advanced simulators where virtual robots can perform millions of interactions, such as manipulation, locomotion, or navigation, accumulating data, in a matter of hours⁷ of processing time, the equivalent of years of operational experience. Subsequently, this knowledge can be transferred

⁶ The massive use of internet data for LLM training has generated intense legal and ethical controversy. Companies like OpenAI, Google, and Meta have faced lawsuits from publishers, authors, and artists who allege unauthorized use of copyrighted content.

⁷ The time required depends on the available hardware. To achieve a timeframe of hours, clusters of GPUs/TPUs are necessary.

to their physical counterparts, reducing costs, risks, and development time.

Applications

The presence of machines and robots with embedded AI represents the most tangible face of what is called Physical AI, systems that have left the laboratory and begun to inhabit factories, hospitals, and public spaces. Despite still being limited in their autonomy, learning capacity, environmental understanding, and even operational safety, several startups have already begun testing their models. Below, I present three examples from distinct areas: medicine, industrial manufacturing, and public safety.

In the field of medicine, an emblematic case is that of Johns Hopkins University. Starting in 2013, researchers led by Axel Krieger, a professor and engineer at the university, began developing the Smart Tissue Autonomous Robot (STAR), with the goal of applying AI to the precise control of soft tissue suturing. After successive experimental iterations, the team demonstrated in 2022 that the system was capable of autonomously performing intestinal anastomosis in animals, achieving precision comparable to, and in some cases surpassing, that of experienced human surgeons. STAR employed advanced computer vision, real-time deformable tissue tracking, and adaptive planning to automatically adjust the trajectory of each suture point as the tissue moved. (Saeidi et al., 2022)

In 2024, the American startup Figure AI⁸ announced the beginning of tests of the Figure 01 humanoid robot at a BMW factory, with a focus on transporting, organizing, and manipulating

components. Despite possessing a degree of autonomy, in this experimental phase the Figure 01 units operate under human supervision. The AI powering Figure AI's humanoid robots is called Helix. Helix is a vision-language-action model designed for the autonomous control of general-purpose humanoid robots, enabling them to understand natural language commands, perceive their environment, and execute complex tasks, such as household chores.

The arrival of Physical AI in the space traditionally dominated by rigid, highly programmed industrial robots marks the beginning of a transition within factories, from deterministic automated systems toward more adaptive and generalist autonomous agents.

One of the areas where the arrival of Physical AI, and humanoid robots in particular, is generating significant discussion is public safety. In March 2025, the police force of Shenzhen, in Guangdong province, China, began testing PM01 humanoid robots, manufactured by the startup EngineAI, in urban patrols alongside human officers. The PM01 integrates multiple depth sensors and LiDAR⁹ for 3D perception of the environment, as well as support for open frameworks (such as ROS¹⁰) and learning algorithms, including reinforcement learning, combining visual, auditory, and spatial data to navigate complex urban environments, execute voice commands, and interact with the public.

Implications for Society

Physical AI cannot be underestimated in its potential to bring about profound changes in society. In some sectors, the impact will be

⁸ Figure AI is an American robotics company founded in 2022 that develops autonomous humanoid robots, such as the Figure 01 and its evolved versions, for physical manipulation in human and industrial environments.

⁹ LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) is an active sensing technology that uses laser pulses to measure distances and generate precise three-dimensional maps of the environment. It is widely used in robotics for navigation, obstacle detection, and spatial mapping, and is also one of the primary sensors employed in autonomous vehicles for perceiving their surroundings, identifying pedestrians, other vehicles, and road infrastructure, thereby contributing to real-time decision-making.

¹⁰ ROS (Robot Operating System) is an open-source framework widely used in robotics research and development, providing libraries and tools for inter-process communication, hardware control, perception, navigation, and sensor integration, facilitating the modular development of complex robotic systems.

greater, given the new capabilities of machines with embedded AI. The manufacturing industry is among the sectors that will feel the effects most acutely. According to a report published by Oxford Economics (2019), 20 million manufacturing jobs could be displaced by 2030 due to robotic automation — a forecast that the researchers themselves acknowledged had underestimated both the pace and the scale of the transformation.

Another sector where Physical AI is driving profound change is logistics and warehousing. Robots designed for moving, sorting, and packaging products are replacing human workers, reshaping not only operational processes but also the profile of jobs available in these environments. A more recent example comes from Amazon: between 2024 and 2025, the company expanded its robotic fleet in distribution centers by more than 250,000 units, integrating computer vision systems and the AI model *DeepFleet*¹¹, which reduced travel time between operations by 10% (Visual Capitalist, 2025).

As humanoid robots expand their artificial cognition and their capacities for perceiving and manipulating objects, the horizon of human labor displacement is set to extend far beyond factories and distribution centers. In a not-too-distant future, sectors such as construction, hospitality, transportation, retail, public safety, and healthcare support, fields that combine basic situational reasoning¹² with physical work involving a certain degree of repetition, will be equally exposed to this transition. The McKinsey Global Institute (2025) reinforces this perspective by identifying that physical tasks make up more than half of the hours worked by approximately 40% of the American workforce — a contingent that includes drivers, construction workers, cooks, and healthcare aides. "We are witnessing the arrival of more sophisticated AI agents,

capable of continuous dialogue, emotional personalization, and growing autonomy." (Murer, 2025)

Conclusion

In Roman mythology, there is a deity called Janus (Janus), associated with beginnings and transitions, depicted with two opposing faces. The figure of Janus appears on arches, gateways, and structures of passage, which have two sides: the one being left behind, and the one yet to come. Every crossing implies, therefore, a choice: once the threshold is crossed, we will be moving toward a new reality. This symbolic duality is one of the most powerful metaphors for understanding the ambiguous nature of technology. Once adopted by society, especially at scale, it is rarely possible to turn back. What unfolds is a gradual and silent transformation, with the formation of new habits, cultural movements, and political reconfigurations. At its furthest extent, entirely new economic structures emerge. Langdon Winner, the American political theorist, argues that technologies are not neutral; they embody specific forms of social organization, distributing power, authority, and control in distinct ways. Any technology, including AI and robotics, thus impacts society at multiple levels: structural, institutional, economic, and cultural. (Winner, 1986)

Physical AI can be regarded as an amplified form of technology, as it seeks to replicate or surpass human cognitive capabilities. Through increasingly sophisticated algorithms for reasoning and decision-making, sensors that approach the complexity of our own senses, and actuators designed to reproduce the dexterity of our hands, we are witnessing only the beginning of this journey.

¹¹ DeepFleet is a reinforcement learning model developed by Amazon to optimize the real-time coordination of robotic fleets within its distribution centers. The system continuously learns from movement patterns, reducing congestion and minimizing travel time between workstations.

¹² Basic situational reasoning is understood here as the capacity to interpret the immediate environment, make simple decisions, and respond to predictable contextual variations.

Driven by investments in the billions of dollars flowing into startups and research centers affiliated with leading universities such as MIT and Stanford, recent studies suggest that the adoption of automation through 2030, encompassing AI agents and robots, could generate approximately \$2.9 trillion in economic value in the United States per year. (Yee et al., 2025) In the medical field alone, considering surgical robotics, hospitals, rehabilitation, and diagnostics, the Physical AI market is projected to grow from \$5.41 billion in 2025 to \$61.19 billion in 2034.

On one side, Physical AI, represented, for example, by autonomous vehicles, carries significant potential for positive social impact: 1.19 million people die annually in traffic accidents, and AI-driven automation could drastically reduce that number through autonomous perception and decision-making technologies. On the other side looms the specter of mass unemployment. According to Morgan Stanley (2025), 75% of occupations could be affected by humanoid robots, impacting approximately 40% of the American workforce, the equivalent of 63 million robotic units in the United States alone.

But there is an even greater risk when Physical AI begins to inhabit our social spaces: decision-making by these autonomous agents. We can envision scenarios in which many of those decisions fall outside the parameters established by their manufacturers — making it inevitable that inappropriate choices will occur, since the world is filled with situations and events that cannot be fully anticipated. Furthermore, no architecture currently exists capable of guaranteeing that the decisions made by these autonomous machines are grounded in the moral values broadly recognized and shared by human society.

We do not yet have an artificial cognition endowed with robust understanding, embedded ethics or moral values, broad contextual adaptation, and truly reliable learning, factors that increase the likelihood of choices that could endanger human lives or cause significant environmental harm.

It is, without doubt, fascinating to watch humanoid robots moving among people on city streets or serving tables in restaurants. But in adopting Physical AI at an accelerated pace, might we not be crossing the portal of Janus too hastily, without reflecting, with the clarity the moment demands, on the consequences for society itself?

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